

1. Introduction

The Escape Time algorithm is a common fractal generation technique [1], first used by Benoît B. Mandelbrot for generating the Mandelbrot set. In the Escape Time algorithm, points where the modulus $|z|$ exceeds the escape radius during the iteration process are drawn as white, while points where the modulus remains within the escape radius are drawn as black. In subsequent research, researchers have proposed additional fractal generation techniques. For example, the Buddhabrot method focuses on tracing the movement trajectories of points in the Mandelbrot set on the complex plane and uses grayscale images to represent the number of times each pixel is hit, thereby forming Mandelbrot sets resembling nebulae [2]. On the other hand, the Pickover Stalk method focuses on finding the closest distance of points on the complex plane to the x -axis and y -axis during the iteration process, leading to the generation of Biomorphs [3]. Biomorphs are biological-looking Pickover Stalks. This method can generate self-similar fractal images resembling single-celled organisms. More types of Pickover Stalks are provided by the orbit trap method [4], not limited to the cross-shaped trap of Pickover Stalk. The orbit trap method can integrate line segments, tangent circles, and even the Mandelbrot set itself [5] into the iterative process of algebraic fractals, thereby generating more diversified fractals.

Inspired by the aforementioned methods, we propose a fractal generation technique using function traps. This method takes points on the complex plane as inputs to a function and determines whether they fall into traps based on the function's output. By constructing various function traps, we obtain a wider variety of Biomorphs fractals, some of which resemble neuron shapes and marine organisms. By employing the L^p -norm framework, we demonstrate that the classical escape time algorithm can be generalized and systematically reproduced as a special case of the function trap method, enabling fractal generation with tunable geometric properties. The Pickover Stalk is a cross-shaped trap aligned with the coordinate axes. Essentially, it measures the distance of points on the complex plane to the axes during the iteration process and selects the minimum value to generate fractals. We found that this method is a special form of function trap, and we also developed a variant of this method using function traps. The Minimum Modulus method [6] and the "Bubble" method [7] focus on constructing fractals using the minimum modulus values of points on the complex plane. We have also developed similar variants using the minimum values of function traps.

2. Key Definitions

Definition 1 (Mandelbrot Set)

For an iterative function $f_c(z) = z^2 + c$, the Mandelbrot set M can be defined as:

$$M = \{c \in \mathbb{C}: f_c^k(0) \not\rightarrow \infty \text{ as } k \rightarrow \infty\}$$

The Mandelbrot Set is a "map" of parameter values c in the complex plane. For each c , we test whether the iterative sequence $z_{i+1} = z_i^2 + c$, starting from $z_0 = 0$, remains bounded (i.e., does not escape to infinity) after a specified number of iterations n . Here z_i represents the value at the i -th iteration step ($1 \leq i \leq n$). If the sequence stays bounded forever, c belongs to the Mandelbrot Set. Visually, the set resembles a cardioid with infinitely many intricate bulbs and filaments. Each bulb corresponds to a unique Julia Set. The boundary of the Mandelbrot Set is infinitely complex, exhibiting self-similarity at all scales.

Definition 2 (Julia Set)

For an iterative function $f_c(z) = z^2 + c$, the filled Julia set $K(f_c)$ of the function can be defined as:

$$K(f_c) = \{z \in \mathbb{C}: f_c^k(z) \not\rightarrow \infty \text{ as } k \rightarrow \infty\}$$

A Julia Set, in contrast, is defined for a fixed parameter c . It represents the set of initial points z_0 in the complex plane for which the sequence $z_{i+1} = z_i^2 + c$ remains bounded after n iterations. The shape of a Julia Set depends critically on c . If c lies within the Mandelbrot Set, the corresponding Julia Set is connected (resembling a single, continuous shape). If c is outside the Mandelbrot Set, the Julia Set becomes disconnected, forming a fractal dust of isolated points.

Definition 3 (Function Trap)

Let $f_c: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be an iterative function defining an algebraic fractal. For a point $c \in \mathbb{C}$, the iteration sequence is defined as

$$I = \{z_0, z_1, z_2, \dots, z_{n-1}\},$$

where $z_i = f_c(z_{i-1})$, n denotes the number of iterations, and $1 \leq i \leq n$. A function trap is a mapping $g: \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ that assigns a non-negative real value to each point in the complex plane during the iteration process. Given a threshold $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}^+$ (referred to as the trap size), the point c is considered to "fall into the trap" if there exists an iteration step i such that $g(z_i) < \varepsilon$. When trapped, the iteration terminates, and the color index of c is computed as $index = g(z_i)/\varepsilon$. If no such $i \leq n$ exists, $index = 0$. By varying $g(z)$ and ε , diverse fractal patterns can be generated. The specific algorithm is outlined as follows:

Algorithm 1: Function Trap Method

Input:

- c , a point in the complex plane
- $f(z)$, algebraic fractal formula
- $g(z)$, function trap
- ε , trap size
- n , number of iterations

Output:

- $index$, color index of the point c
 - 1: $i \leftarrow 1$
 - 2: $z_0 \leftarrow c$
 - 3: $index \leftarrow 0$
 - 4: **while** $i \leq n$ **do**
 - 5: $z_i \leftarrow f(z_{i-1})$
 - 6: **if** $g(z_i) < \varepsilon$ **then**
 - 7: $index \leftarrow g(z_i) / \varepsilon$
 - 8: **return** $index$
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: $i \leftarrow i + 1$
 - 11: **end while**
 - 12: **return** $index$
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3. Main Theoretical Results

Theorem 3.1 (Generalized Escape Time Algorithm)

The standard escape time algorithm is a special case of the function trap method when the trap function is chosen as $g(z) = \|z\|_p^{-1}$, where $\|z\|_p$ denotes the L^p - norm. Under this framework, the condition $g(z_i) < \varepsilon$ is equivalent to $\|z_i\|_p > \varepsilon^{-1}$. Specifically, when $p = 2$, this reduces to the standard escape time algorithm.

Proof

For a complex number $z = Re(z) + iIm(z)$, its L^p - norm defined as:

$$\|z\|_p = (|Re(z)|^p + |Im(z)|^p)^{1/p}$$

where $Re(z)$ represents the real part of the complex number z and $Im(z)$ represents the imaginary part of z . The corresponding trap function is:

$$g(z) = \|z\|_p^{-1} = \frac{1}{(|Re(z)|^p + |Im(z)|^p)^{1/p}}$$

Starting from the trap function definition, the condition $g(z_i) < \varepsilon$ expands to:

$$\frac{1}{(|Re(z_i)|^p + |Im(z_i)|^p)^{1/p}} < \varepsilon$$

Assuming $\|z_i\|_p \neq 0$, taking reciprocals on both sides:

$$(|Re(z_i)|^p + |Im(z_i)|^p)^{1/p} > \varepsilon^{-1}$$

This simplifies to:

$$\|z_i\|_p > \varepsilon^{-1}$$

Thus, $g(z_i) < \varepsilon$ if and only if $\|z_i\|_p > \varepsilon^{-1}$. When $p = 2$, the L^2 -norm corresponds to the Euclidean norm:

$$\|z\|_2 = \sqrt{|Re(z)|^2 + |Im(z)|^2}$$

The trap function becomes:

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{|Re(z)|^2 + |Im(z)|^2}} = \frac{1}{|z|}$$

Here, $g(z_i) < \varepsilon$ is equivalent to:

$$|z_i| > \varepsilon^{-1}$$

which matches the escape criterion in the classical escape time algorithm. Therefore, for $p = 2$, the function trap method fully reduces to the standard escape time algorithm.

Proposition 3.2 (Pickover Stalk as a Special Case of the Function Trap Method)

The traditional Pickover Stalk method is equivalent to the function trap method with the trap function:

$$g(z) = \min\{|Re(z)|, |Im(z)|\}$$

This function trap preserves the core logic of proximity-based trapping.

Proof

Define the function trap as:

$$g(z) = \min\{|Re(z)|, |Im(z)|\}$$

where \min denotes the minimum value in the set. A point z_i falls into the trap if $g(z_i) < \varepsilon$. This is mathematically equivalent to:

$$\min\{|Re(z)|, |Im(z)|\} < \varepsilon$$

By the properties of the minimum operator, this inequality holds if and only if at least one of the following is true:

$$|Re(z_i)| < \varepsilon \text{ or } |Im(z_i)| < \varepsilon$$

This matches the "OR" condition in the Pickover Stalk method. This inequality implies that z_i is trapped if either its real or imaginary component falls within ε of the coordinate axes, which is the core logic of the Pickover Stalk method.

4. Experimental Validation

4.1 “Sea Anemone” Method

The "Sea Anemone" method employs the L^p - norm to construct function traps. For a complex number $z = Re(z) + iIm(z)$, the function trap is defined as:

$$g(z) = \|z\|_p^{-1} = \frac{1}{(|Re(z)|^p + |Im(z)|^p)^{1/p}}$$

Two specific instances were tested:

1. Case $p = 0.5$:

$$g_1(z) = \frac{1}{(|Re(z)|^{1/2} + |Im(z)|^{1/2})^2}$$

Applying Algorithm 1 with $g_1(z)$ and $\varepsilon = 0.12$ generated biomorphic fractals resembling sea anemones (Fig. 1, left).

2. Case $p = 2$:

$$g_2(z) = \frac{1}{(|Re(z)|^2 + |Im(z)|^2)^{1/2}}$$

Using $g_2(z)$ with $\varepsilon = 0.12$ reproduced the traditional escape-time algorithm (Fig. 1, right), demonstrating the method's generality.

Fig.1 Biomorphic fractal image generated using function trap $g_1(z)$ and Algorithm 1 (left); fractal generated using function trap $g_2(z)$ and Algorithm 1, reproducing the escape-time algorithm (right).

4.2 Neuron Method

The Neuron Method utilizes the logarithmic product of real and imaginary components:

$$g_3(z) = |\log(Re(z))| \cdot |\log(Im(z))|$$

The $\log(x)$ function in this method represents a complex logarithm, i.e.,

$$\log(x) = \ln|x| + iArgx + 2k\pi i, \quad (x \neq 0)$$

For the function trap $g_3(z)$, we only consider the cases where $k = 0$ and $x \in \mathbb{R}$, thus:

$$\log(x) = \begin{cases} \ln|x| + \pi i, & \text{if } x < 0 \\ \ln x, & \text{if } x > 0 \end{cases}$$

Applying Algorithm 1 with the function trap $g_3(z)$ generates biomorphs resembling neurons. Figure 2 shows function trap images associated with the Mandelbrot set (left, $\varepsilon = 0.2$) and the Julia set (right, $\varepsilon = 0.04$).

Fig.2 Function trap images associated with the Mandelbrot set (left) and Julia set with $c = 0.6 + 0.3i$ (right), generated using Algorithm 1 with the function trap $g_3(z)$. Trap sizes $\varepsilon = 0.2$ (left, Mandelbrot variant) and $\varepsilon = 0.04$ (right, Julia variant) were used.

4.3 Extended Pickover Stalk Method

The Pickover Stalk method was extended via two function traps:

1. Traditional Cross Trap:

$$g_4(z) = \min\{|Re(z)|, |Im(z)|\}$$

With $\varepsilon = 0.02$, Algorithm 1 generated classic cross-shaped biomorphs (Fig. 3, left).

2. Multiplicative Variant:

$$g_5(z) = |Re(z)| \cdot |Im(z)|$$

Using $\varepsilon = 0.005$, the resulting fractals exhibited similar but denser structures (Fig. 3, right).

Fig.3 Traditional Pickover Stalk method (left) and variant generated by the function trap method (right).

4.4 Extended Minimum Modulus Method

The Minimum Modulus method was generalized using:

1. Euclidean Norm Trap:

$$g_6(z) = \sqrt{Re(z)^2 + Im(z)^2}$$

Algorithm 2 (described below) with $\varepsilon = 0.5$ reproduced the "Bubble" method (Fig. 4, left).

2. Manhattan Norm Variant:

$$g_7(z) = |R(z)| + |I(z)|$$

Setting $\varepsilon = 0.6$ generated fractals with angular features (Fig. 4, right).

Algorithm 2 captures persistent minimum value m , essential for methods like the "Bubble" technique, which relies on the smallest modulus encountered during the entire iteration process. This method requires some adjustments to Algorithm 1 in order to obtain the minimum value m . The specific algorithm is as follows:

Algorithm 2: Minimum Value Function Trap Method

Input:

c , a point in the complex plane
 $f(z)$, algebraic fractal formula
 $g(z)$, function trap
 ε , trap size
 n , number of iterations

Output:

$index$, color index of the point c

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1:  $i \leftarrow 1$ 
2:  $z_0 \leftarrow 0$ 
3:  $m \leftarrow \text{MAX\_VALUE}$ 
4:  $index \leftarrow 0$ 
5: while  $i \leq n$  do
6:    $z_i \leftarrow f(z_{i-1})$ 
7:   if  $g(z_i) < m$  then
8:      $m \leftarrow g(z_i)$ 
9:   end if
10:   $i \leftarrow i + 1$ 
11: end while
12: if  $m < \varepsilon$  then
13:    $index \leftarrow m / \varepsilon$ 
14: end if
15: return  $index$ 
```

The constant MAX_VALUE in Algorithm 2 should be set to a sufficiently large value to facilitate obtaining the minimum value m .

Fig.4 Traditional "bubble" method (left) and variant generated by the function trap method (right).

5. Implementation details

In the article, all images were generated using Matlab with a pixel range of 4096 in length and 2048 in width. The complex plane region used was $[-2.8, 2.8] \times [-1.4, 1.4]$. Figure 5 displays the color bar used. The iteration function utilized was $z_i = z_{i-1}^2 + c$. All constructed function traps $g(z)$ are presented in Table 1. The source code for generating all images and implementing the function trap methods described in this paper is publicly available on GitHub:

<https://github.com/Fractalstructure/FunctionTrapFractal>

Fig.5 Colors used in Figure 1 to Figure 4.

Table 1 Function trap

Formula	Trap size
$g_1(z) = 1/(Re(z) ^{0.5} + Im(z) ^{0.5})^2$	0.12
$g_2(z) = 1/(Re(z) ^2 + Im(z) ^2)^{1/2}$	0.12
$g_3(z) = \log(Re(z)) \cdot \log(Im(z)) $	0.2 (Mandelbrot set) and 0.04 (Julia set)
$g_4(z) = \min\{ Re(z) , Im(z) \}$	0.02
$g_5(z) = Re(z) \cdot Im(z) $	0.005
$g_6(z) = \sqrt{Re(z)^2 + Im(z)^2}$	0.5
$g_7(z) = Re(z) + Im(z) $	0.6

where $Re(z)$ represents the real part of the complex number z , $Im(z)$ represents the imaginary part of z

6. Conclusion and Future Prospects

This paper proposes a method for constructing fractals using function traps, which extends the traditional Pickover biomorphs method and Pickover Stalk method. By employing different function traps, this method generates more diversified biomorphs fractals. Crucially, our L^p -norm framework unifies classical fractal generation techniques—such as the escape time algorithm—under the function trap paradigm, demonstrating their mathematical coherence. To better observe the effectiveness of this method, we only utilized the most basic fractal iteration formula: $z_i = z_{i-1}^2 + c$. However, by using more complex iteration formulas such as Newton's method and its variants [8, 9, 10], non-standard complex numbers [11], etc., as additional methods, even more varieties of biomorphs fractals can be obtained.

In future research, we can focus on the entire iteration process of fractals. For example, the difference in phase angle between the i th and j th iterations of a point on the complex plane can be utilized as an index: $index = |\theta_i - \theta_j|$. Additionally, other parameters during the iteration process may

also be advantageous for constructing new fractals.

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